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INTERACTIVE DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY SKILLS REQUIRED FOR VIRTUAL TEACHING AND LEARNING OF BUSINESS EDUCATION COURSES IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN ABIA STATE.

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DOI: [https://doi.org/
10.5281/zenodo.17434931](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17434931)

Abstract

The study examined interactive digital technology skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in Tertiary Institutions in Abia State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study was a descriptive survey design. The population of the study consist of 26 lecturers from tertiary institutions in Abia State offering Business Education courses. The entire population was used because it was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire which was structured along a four-point scale. The data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation, and t-test statistics. Mean was used to answer research questions while standard deviation was used to ascertain the closeness and homogeneity of the response items. The hypotheses were tested using the t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significant. The findings revealed among others that Business Educators required digital literacy skills, digital database skills, for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions. The findings further revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital data literacy skills, and digital database skills, required for teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that Business Educators should acquire relevant digital skills essential to remain relevant in the current technological changes.

Keywords: *Interactive, Digital Technology, Skills, Visual Teaching and learning and Business Education.*

Introduction

Digital technology has led to a tremendous development in all fields of endeavour especially education. It has changed the way people access

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information as well as human interactions and communication. According to Ademiluyi and Akande (2023), digital technology has transformed various jobs, thus impacting positively on the economy and society. Digital technology signifies wide range of technologies, tools services and applications using various types of hardware and software. Similarly, Zakka, Bewaran and Moris (2021) noted that digital technology facilitates services or activities by electronic means to create, store, process, transmit and display information. This electronic technology required acquired skills.

Skills is the art of possessing the ability to power, authority, or competency to do the task required of an individual on the job. Tajudeen (2014) defines skill as a special ability or expertise to do something well, which is by learning and having undergone a particular training exercise. So, when we talk about digital skill, they are all set of skills needed to effectively and efficiently perform office tasks using new technologies in the digital environment (Okoji, Nwankwo, Anene & Olorunfemi 2020). According to Heinz (2020), digital skills are skills needed to use digital devices, communication application and networks to access and manage information from basic online searching to specialist programming and development. In the view of Lyashenko (2016), it is a continuum of skills to communicate, collaborate and solve problems for effective and creative self-fulfilment in life, learning, work, and social activities.

Digital technology skills on the other hand involves

the ability, confident, critical thinking and responsible use of and engagement with digital technologies for learning, at work and for

participation in society. It includes information data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation including programming safety, digital well-being and competencies related to cyber security and problem solving (UNESCO, 2020). These digital technology tools include computers (desktop and laptops), smart phones, scanners, digital photocopies, internet and audio/video conferencing facilities among others. Furthermore, Offili (2017) opined that a digitally skilled employee that want a decent work in the office should have the skill to use computer both desktops and laptops and other electronic devices to complete office tasks. Digital technology skills constitute one of the five fundamental pillars of the digital economy for Africa. The other foundational pillars are digital technology infrastructure, digital technology platform, digital technology financial services and digital technology entrepreneurship (World Bank Group, 2020). Digital technology skills are very important in the development of individual and the nation as it supports effective communication, increase efficiency, enables creativity, improves security, and evaluate information among others. These skills can improve one's confidence to use technology for work, learning and daily life activities. In the same vein, Hirsch (2016) noted that digital skills include ability to use various devices for tasks, find information on the internet, communicate socially and professionally using e-mail and social media platform, bank, shop, access services or apply for jobs online among others.

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State. Business Educators are those who have undergone training in Business Teacher Education programme.

Business Education is unit of vocational education which involves acquisition of skills, knowledge and competences which makes the recipient proficient in business. According to Umoru and Jimoh (2020), Business Education is a conglomerate of courses that is concerned with the acquisition, development, and inculcation of the proper values for the survival of the individual and the society. It helps individuals to acquire saleable skills that will enable them fit into various business organizations or be self-employed in the absence of paid employment hence Nwokike and Ezenwafor (2021) asserted that Business Education is a skill-oriented programme directed towards equipping the recipients with relevant skills for success in paid or self-employment. It also equip the recipients with the pedagogical skills for teaching and learning. Teaching and learning form the core of the educational system. According to Duktur (2015), teaching is an active and constructive process in which the teacher assumes the role of a strategic planner, making decisions about the content and the appropriate instructional strategies. Days are gone when teaching and learning were considered in the four walls of the classroom. It can be carried out virtually. Virtual teaching and learning are a learning experience that is enhanced through utilizing computer and/or the internet both outside and inside the facilities of the educational organization. Virtual teaching and learning most commonly take place in

an online environment. Singh and Thurman (2019) noted that teaching activities are carried out online whereby the teacher and the learner are physically

separated in terms of place, time or both. To this effect, Ekwue, Anyeabunam and Alfa (2016) opined that the increased use of new technologies in Business Education makes teaching and learning increasingly flexible, multi-tasking and performance based, hence the need for Business Education teachers to acquire the necessary skills needed to be able to teach effectively using the interactive digital data literacy skill, digital communication skills, content creation skills, database skills and desktop publishing skills required to the learners. Interactive digital data literacy is defined as the ability of the Business Educator to use knowledge and communication technology to identify, assess, produce, and convey information, involving both cognitive and technological skills. According to onwubuya, okoli and Uteh (2023), data literacy is more than just the ability to use apps or use a digital device rather it is a wide range of nuanced cognitive, motor, sociological and emotional skills required by Business Educators to work efficiently in digital environment such as the use of teaching and research. Okeji, Nwankwo, Anene and Olorunfemi (2020) view data literacy as the ability to comprehend knowledge and exercise digital activities in a digital world. Interactive digital data literacy skills aim to strengthen teachers' ability to identify and deal with their own and their students' needs for data and information. According to Mshelia (2019), for one to be relevant in today's global workplace, computer and digital skills are relevant for all Business Educators, for students and

secretaries as most business and office functions have been simplified through automation. Data literacy skills address several abilities and concepts

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that can help us determine exactly what our needs in terms of information, data and digital content under various circumstances are. Interactive database skill is also relevant in the current era of new technologies. Interactive databased skills are an organised collection of structured information, or data, typically stored electronically in a computer system. Muhammed, Adnan, Muhammed, Muhammed, Uzma, Kamran & Mamoun (2025) defined it as an integrated collection of logically related records or files consolidated into a common pool that provides data for one or multiple uses. A databased is usually controlled by a database management system (DBMS). Digital database skill is the technical knowledge or ability to store, access and retrieve organised collection of data that are related to a particular field (Alberto, 2013). To excel in the digital world, the database skill required include the ability to identify fields, records data attributes, insert, delete, and upload record, use structured query language, web database programming, identify primary and foreign keys, create relationships, extract database objects, knowledge of disk storage files systems and file structures among others (Ademiluyi, Adegboye & Akande, 2022). There is no gender bias in acquisition of interactive digital skills among Business Educators. It is a necessary skill for both male and female Business Educators. Gender has a lot of impact to play in teaching and learning. Gender is a social creation resulting from biological identities as noted by Nnachi in Ndom-Uchendu and

Ezeabii (2023). Boys and girls should have equal and full accesses to all levels of education including the tertiary institutions.

Tertiary institutions are an institution of higher learning owned and managed by either State or Federal Government and private individuals. Federal tertiary institutions are institutions managed and controlled by the Federal Government while the State tertiary institutions are institutions managed and controlled by the State Government. It is basically at this level of higher institution that this interactive digital technology users specialises in their area of interest. The use of interactive digital technologies for pedagogical delivery has undoubtedly affected teaching, learning and research. Olisa (2014) opined that the integration of these technologies into the school system can help revitalize teachers and students alike. It has the great potentials to support education across curriculum including Business Education curriculum and this provides opportunities for an effective communication between teachers and students in ways that have not been possible before (Utoware, Ken-Ikidi & Apreala, 2016). It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to determine the interactive digital technology skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Statement of the Problem

Interactive digital technology are tools that facilitate independent learning and give way to new scenario which favours both individuals and collaborative learning. However, it seems that most institutions in Nigeria have not been able to embrace virtual teaching and learning using interactive digital

technologies to the detriment of the students and the society at large. If required interactive digital skills by are not acquired by Business Educators, it may

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result in producing graduates that may not be relevant in 21st century workplace.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study is to determine interactive digital technology skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State. Specifically, the study intends to determine the:

1. Interactive digital data literacy skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.
2. Interactive digital database skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the interactive digital data literacy skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions.
2. What are the interactive digital database skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significant.

H0₁ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital data literacy skill

required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions.

H0₄ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital database skill required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions.

Methodology

The study is a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consist of 26 Business Educators from four government own tertiary institutions in Abia State offering Business Education. One Federal University, One State University, one college of Education and one Polytechnic. Census sampling technique was adopted because the population is small. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the research after extensive literature review titled “Interactive Digital Technology Skills Required for Virtual Teaching and Learning of Business Education Courses Questionnaire (IDTSRVTLBECQ)”. The questionnaire was made up of two sections, A and B. Section A is a biodata while section B contains 22 items questions which was based on the purpose of the study. Interactive digital technology skills required was structured along a four-point scale of Very High Required (VHR), High Required (HR), Required (R), and Not Required (NR), weighing (4) points, (3) points, (2) points and (1) point respectively. The instrument was validated by experts in Business and Entrepreneurship Education Department, Enugu State University of Science and Technology and Measurement and Evaluation

Department of Abia State University, Uturu. The instrument was subjected to reliability using Cronbach Alpha. The result yielded a reliability

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index of 0.86 and this was considered adequate for the study. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics.

Results

Research Question One: What are the interactive digital data literacy skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Table 1: Interactive Digital Data Literacy Skills Required for Virtual Teaching and Learning of Business Education Courses in Tertiary Institutions.

Interactive digital information and data literacy skills required include the ability to:	Mean	Std
Access information online through computers	3.31	.928
Network with other colleagues via computer	2.08	.935
Use graphic tablet to download files	2.50	.860
Use audiotapes in teaching and learning	2.69	.970
Type and print notes for students with computer	3.38	.697
Present lessons on PowerPoint	2.85	.834
Use social media sites like LinkedIn, Facebook, and twitter to share course resources with students	2.73	.919
Engage in online communications	2.77	.863
Use computer, phones and laptops	2.69	.928
Use a working e-mail account to send out course works and assignments to students	2.77	.863
Use scanning machines to convert course materials to soft copies	3.08	.891
Use the photocopying machines to make extra copies of office documents	2.73	1.041
	2.79	

Table 1 reveals the interactive digital information and data literacy skills required for virtual teaching and learning Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State. Majority of the items revealed mean scores above the criterion benchmark of 2.50 in 11 out of the 12 items. Further, the grand mean of 2.79 shows that Business Educators require almost all the interactive digital information and data literacy skills for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Research Question Four: What are the interactive digital database skills required for virtual teaching and

learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Table 2: Interactive Digital Database Skills Required for Virtual Teaching and Learning of Business Education Courses in Tertiary Institutions

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S/No	The interactive digital database skills required are the ability to:	Mean	Std. Dev.
	Identify fields with unique values	2.35	.936
	Create database tables and record data	2.19	.981
	Query different data attributes from a database	2.42	.902
	Harmonise and refine database design	2.12	.909
	Extract database objects	2.38	.941
	Use web database programming effectively	2.15	.925
	Insert, update and delete record in a database	2.12	1.071
	Use information system and system structure	3.23	.765
	Use file security and security techniques in managing database	2.23	.951
	Use structured query language (SQL) e	1.96	.958
		2.31	

Table 2 shows the summary of the interactive digital database skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State. All items revealed mean scores below the criterion benchmark of 2.50 except item 8 which is on use information systems and systems structure. This therefore indicates that Business Educators require the skill in that area and not necessarily needing the other items to teach and learn Business Education courses virtually. With a grand mean score of 2.31, respondents disagreed to requiring the skills outlined for virtual teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Test of Hypotheses

H0₁ One: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital data literacy skill required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test of Significant Difference between the Mean Responses of Male and Female Business Educators on Interactive Digital Data Literacy Skill Required for Virtual Teaching and Learning of Business Education Courses in Tertiary Institutions

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	Sig. 2-tailed	Decision
Male	14	2.8155	.33362	24	.782	Accept Ho
Female	12	2.7778	.35236			

The result presented on table 3 shows the summary of summary of t-test of no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital data literacy skill required for

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virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State. It shows the mean score and standard deviation for male to be (2.81 and 0.333) and (2.77 and 0.352) for female, with a Df of 24. The p-value of 0.782 which was found to be greater than the significance level of 0.05 meant that the hypothesis was accepted and retained as stated; There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital data literacy skill required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital database skill required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test of Significant Difference between the Mean Responses of Male and Female Business Educators on Interactive Digital Databases Skill Required for Virtual Teaching and Learning of Business Education Courses in Tertiary Institutions

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	Sig. 2-tailed	Decision
Male	14	2.25	.336	24	.272	Accept Ho
Female	12	2.39	.299			

The result presented on table 4 shows the summary of summary of t-test of no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital databases skill required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State. It shows the mean score and standard deviation for male to be (2.25 and 0.336) and (2.39 and 0.299) for female, with a Df of 24. The p-value of 0.272 which was found to be greater than the significance level of 0.05 indicates that the hypothesis was accepted and retained as stated; There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital database skill required for virtual

The study sought to find out the interactive digital technology skills required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State. From the findings of the study in table 1, it was revealed that Business Educators required data literacy skills in teaching and learning of Business Education courses hence all the item questions was above the criterion benchmark of 2.50 except one. this result is consistent with Mshelia (2019) who noted that to be relevant in today’s global workplace, computer and digital skills are relevant for all Business Educators, students and secretaries as most business and office functions have been simplified through automation. The study also revealed in hypothesis 1 that there is

teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Abia State.

Discussions of Findings

no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital data literacy skills required for

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virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institution. This indicates that both male and female Business Educators do not differed in their opinions of the interactive digital data literacy skills they required for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education in tertiary institutions in Abia State. The findings in table 2 shows that all the items question are below the criterion benchmark of 2.50 except item no. 8 which is on use information system and system structure. This indicated that Business Educators require the skill in that area and not necessarily needing the other items to teach and learn Business Education courses virtually. The grand mean of 2.31 indicated that the respondents are of the view that Business Educators do not necessarily require digital database skills for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions. This is in consonant with Alberto (2013) who said that the essence of digital database skill is to store, maintain and retrieve database information conveniently, quickly, and efficiently. The hypothesis findings also revealed that there are no significant differences in the mean responses of male and female Business Educators on interactive digital database skills required for teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions. Since there is no disparity in gender view on the mean responses on interactive digital database skills required for teaching and learning implies that no special training session is required for obtaining this skill.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that interactive digital technology skills for virtual teaching and learning of Business Education courses

are required. Such digital technology skills as digital literacy skills, and digital database skills should be acquired by Business Educators in order to enhance teaching and learning of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions. However, Government should be committed to the implementation of policies that will propel the development and deployment of digital technologies in the educational system.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made

1. Business Educators should ensure that they acquire relevant digital skills essentials to remain relevant in the current global settings. Such skills as will be gotten from digital data literacy and digital data base skills are very vital.
2. Business Educators should update their knowledge on digital skills through training, workshops, conferences and research to meet the current trends and professional demands of the present times.

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